

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Environmental costs of potato production in Galicia: impact of reducing phosphate fertilizers and using mycorrhizae

Assessing the environmental costs of different agricultural practices is key to developing more sustainable management strategies in European agroecosystems. This study analyses the impact of phosphate fertilizer reduction and combination with mycorrhizal inoculants on the sustainability of potato production in Galicia. This information is crucial for policy makers to promote sustainable agricultural policies that reduce dependence on chemical inputs without compromising productivity.

The environmental cost-benefit analysis (e-CBA) monetizes the environmental impacts identified by the life cycle analysis (LCA) and allows a comparison of different practices in terms of environmental costs (€ impact per € gross margin for the farmer). The results show that the elimination of phosphate fertilizers, either alone or together with the application of mycorrhiza (T3 and T5), reduces environmental costs by 8%

compared to conventional practices (0.19 €/€). However, a partial reduction of these fertilizers (T2) reduces crop yields without proportionally reducing the impact, leading to an increase in environmental costs of up to 27%.

The fertilization strategy influences the extent of the environmental impact but does not significantly change the type of environmental impact caused. For all practices analysed, 90% of the environmental costs come from global warming, marine eutrophication, terrestrial acidification, and fine particulate matter formation.

In terms of environmental efficiency, the complete elimination of phosphate fertilizers (alone or with mycorrhizal application) improves the profitability of the system by optimizing the relationship between revenues and environmental costs.

1. Environmental costs (€ per € gross margin for the farmer) for each practice tested.

2. Percentage of impact categories responsible for the calculated environmental costs.

KEYWORDS

Environmental costs, potato production, phosphate fertilization, mycorrhizae, e-CBA, sustainability

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

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